

ISic1397

I.Sicily inscription 1397

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.09.11

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Purchased 1914

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 35826

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140904

1. Γλυκέρ-
2. α χρηστ-
3. ἄ χαῖρε,
4. ἔζησες
5. ἔτη νγ'. □
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493012

EDCS 39101524

PHI 140904

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0578 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Ansaldi, F. 1851. I monumenti dell'antica Centuripi. Centuripae. At 51 no.14

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